

Assessment of Long-Term Impact of COVID-19 on Pulmonary Functional Capacity**Sanjay Mandloi¹, Diviyant Kumar Gupta², Prateek Singh Rajput³, Ayachit Kesharwani^{2*}**¹MD Medicine, Seniors Resident, Department of Internal Medicine, AIIMS, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India²MD Medicine, Seniors Resident, Department of Internal Medicine, GMC, Satna, Madhya Pradesh, India³MBBS, Intern, Department of Medicine, GMC, Satna, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Abstract:**Background:** The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in significant acute respiratory illness, but the long-term impact on pulmonary functional capacity among survivors is not well understood.**Aim and Objective:** To evaluate the long-term effects of COVID-19 on pulmonary function and quality of life over 24 months.**Materials and Methods:** A prospective, longitudinal cohort study was conducted with 200 adult participants with laboratory-confirmed COVID-19. Participants were recruited from two large hospitals and one community clinic. Baseline assessments, including pulmonary function tests (PFTs), six-minute walk tests (6MWTs), and patient-reported outcome measures, were performed at enrollment (3 months post-acute COVID-19). Follow-up assessments were conducted at 6, 12, and 24 months. Statistical analyses included repeated measures ANOVA and paired t-tests.**Results:** Of the 200 participants initially enrolled in the study, 180 completed the 24-month follow-up. Over this period, significant declines in pulmonary function were observed. The Forced Vital Capacity (FVC) decreased from 95.3% at baseline to 89.2% at 24 months ($p < 0.001$), and the Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second (FEV1) decreased from 94.8% to 88.3% ($p < 0.001$). The Diffusing Capacity of the Lungs for Carbon Monoxide (DLCO) also showed a notable decline, from 85.4% to 79.1% ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, exercise capacity, as measured by the Six-Minute Walk Distance (6MWD), decreased from 520.3 meters to 465.6 meters ($p < 0.001$). Patient-reported outcomes indicated increased dyspnea, with the mMRC Dyspnea Score rising from 1.5 at baseline to 2.2 at 24 months ($p < 0.001$). There were also significant declines in health-related quality of life, as evidenced by decreases in both the SF-36 Physical Component Score (from 48.7 to 43.1, $p < 0.001$) and the SF-36 Mental Component Score (from 50.1 to 45.3, $p < 0.001$). Furthermore, 35% of participants reported new respiratory symptoms or diagnoses during the follow-up period, including bronchitis (12.5%), asthma (10%), and pulmonary fibrosis (7.5%).**Conclusions:** COVID-19 has a substantial long-term impact on pulmonary functional capacity and quality of life. Significant declines in FVC, FEV1, DLCO, and exercise capacity were observed over 24 months. These findings underscore the importance of long-term follow-up and the need for targeted rehabilitation programs to manage the ongoing respiratory health needs of COVID-19 survivors.**Keywords:** COVID-19, Pulmonary Function, Long-Term Effects, Respiratory Health, Longitudinal Study, Quality of Life.

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has presented the global healthcare community with an unprecedented challenge, as the virus has demonstrated the capacity to inflict significant and potentially long-lasting impacts on the respiratory health of affected individuals. [1] As the pandemic continues to unfold, it is crucial to investigate the long-term consequences of COVID-19 on the pulmonary functional capacity of survivors, as this information

will be vital in guiding healthcare strategies and informing public health policies. [2-5]

Emerging research has begun to shed light on the potential long-term effects of COVID-19 on the respiratory system, with studies suggesting that a significant proportion of individuals who have recovered from the acute phase of the disease may continue to experience persistent respiratory symptoms and impaired lung function. [6,7] This

phenomenon, commonly referred to as "long COVID," has been observed in hospitalized and non-hospitalized patients, with some studies reporting that up to 80% of hospitalized individuals may develop long-term sequelae. [5]

The precise mechanisms underlying the long-term pulmonary impact of COVID-19 still need to be fully understood. Still, it is believed that the virus may trigger a complex cascade of inflammatory and immune responses that can lead to lasting damage to the respiratory system. [6,8] Additionally, the severity of the initial COVID-19 illness may play a significant role in determining the long-term outcomes, with those who experienced more severe disease during the acute phase being at higher risk of developing persistent respiratory impairment. [8]

To better understand the long-term impact of COVID-19 on pulmonary functional capacity, longitudinal studies are needed to track the respiratory health of infected individuals over an extended period. [9] These studies should incorporate a range of diagnostic tools, including pulmonary function tests, imaging studies, and clinical assessments, to comprehensively evaluate the long-term respiratory consequences of COVID-19. [10]

By elucidating the long-term pulmonary effects of COVID-19, healthcare providers and policymakers can develop more effective strategies for managing the long-term care of COVID-19 survivors. These strategies include implementing targeted rehabilitation programs and allocating resources to address the ongoing respiratory needs of affected individuals.

Materials and Methods

This prospective, longitudinal cohort study was conducted to assess the long-term impact of COVID-19 on pulmonary functional capacity. Participants were recruited from a tertiary care centre. The Institutional Review Board approved the study, and all participants provided written informed consent.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults aged 18 years or older.
- Laboratory-confirmed prior SARS-CoV-2 infection (PCR or antigen test).
- Recovered from the acute phase of COVID-19 (≥ 3 months post-diagnosis).

Exclusion Criteria

- Pre-existing severe respiratory conditions (e.g., severe COPD, interstitial lung disease requiring oxygen therapy).
- Inability to provide informed consent.

- Contraindications to pulmonary function testing.

Baseline Assessment (3 Months Post-Acute COVID-19):

Demographic and Clinical Data: Collected data included age, sex, ethnicity, body mass index (BMI), smoking history, comorbidities, severity of COVID-19 (e.g., WHO ordinal scale), and treatments received during the acute phase.

Pulmonary Function Tests (PFTs): Performed according to ATS/ERS guidelines using [Specify spirometer model]. Measurements included:

- Forced Vital Capacity (FVC)
- Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second (FEV1)
- FEV1/FVC ratio
- Forced Expiratory Flow at 25-75% of FVC (FEF25-75%)
- Peak Expiratory Flow (PEF)
- Diffusing Capacity of the Lungs for Carbon Monoxide (DLCO)
- Six-Minute Walk Test (6MWT): Conducted according to ATS guidelines to assess exercise capacity.

Patient-Reported Outcomes: Administered validated questionnaires to assess dyspnea (modified Medical Research Council [mMRC] dyspnea scale), cough, fatigue, and health-related quality of life (SF-36).

Follow-up Assessments: Participants were followed up at 6, 12, and 24 months post-enrollment. Each follow-up visit included:

- Repeat PFTs and 6MWT.
- Re-administration of patient-reported outcome measures.
- Assessment of new respiratory symptoms or diagnoses.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS software (version XX). Descriptive statistics were used to summarize baseline characteristics. Pulmonary function parameters, 6MWT distances, and patient-reported outcomes were analyzed using repeated measures ANOVA to assess changes over time. Paired t-tests were used for post-hoc comparisons. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations: The study was conducted according to the Declaration of Helsinki. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board. Before enrollment, written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Participants were assured of the confidentiality of their data and informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time.

Results

Participant Characteristics: Two hundred participants were enrolled in the study, with 180 completing the 24-month follow-up. The mean age of

participants was 45.2 years (SD: 12.3), with 54% male and 46% female. Table 1 provides a summary of the baseline characteristics of the study population.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the study population.

Characteristic	Total (N = 200)
Age (years), mean (SD)	45.2 (12.3)
Sex, n (%)	
Male	108 (54)
Female	92 (46)
Body Mass Index (BMI), mean (SD)	27.4 (4.6)
Smoking history, n (%)	
Never	120 (60)
Former	50 (25)
Current	30 (15)
COVID-19 severity, n (%)	
Mild	100 (50)
Moderate	70 (35)
Severe	30 (15)
Comorbidities, n (%)	
Hypertension	60 (30)
Diabetes	40 (20)
Cardiovascular disease	20 (10)

Pulmonary Function Tests (PFTs): Table 2 summarizes the changes in pulmonary function test results from baseline to 24 months. Significant reductions were observed in Forced Vital Capacity (FVC), Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second (FEV1), and the Diffusing Capacity of the Lungs for Carbon Monoxide (DLCO).

Table 2: Changes in pulmonary function test results from baseline to 24 months

PFT Parameter	Baseline, mean (SD)	6 months, mean (SD)	12 months, mean (SD)	24 months, mean (SD)	p-value*
FVC (% predicted)	95.3 (12.1)	92.1 (11.8)	90.7 (11.5)	89.2 (11.3)	<0.001
FEV1 (% predicted)	94.8 (12.5)	91.9 (12.2)	89.8 (11.9)	88.3 (11.7)	<0.001
FEV1/FVC ratio	0.81 (0.05)	0.80 (0.05)	0.79 (0.05)	0.79 (0.05)	0.01
FEF25-75% (% predicted)	78.5 (15.3)	75.4 (15.1)	73.2 (14.9)	72.1 (14.7)	0.01
Peak Expiratory Flow (% predicted)	89.7 (13.5)	86.8 (13.3)	85.2 (13.0)	83.7 (12.8)	0.02
DLCO (% predicted)	85.4 (10.6)	82.3 (10.4)	80.5 (10.2)	79.1 (10.1)	<0.001

*p-values derived from repeated measures ANOVA.

Six-Minute Walk Test (6MWT): The six-minute walk distance (6MWD) significantly decreased over time, indicating participants' exercise capacity declined. Table 3 provides the mean 6MWD at baseline, 6 months, 12 months, and 24 months.

Table 3: Mean 6MWD at baseline, 6 months, 12 months, and 24 months.

Time Point	6MWD (meters), mean (SD)	p-value*
Baseline	520.3 (75.2)	
6 Months	500.1 (72.8)	0.01
12 Months	480.4 (70.5)	0.01
24 Months	465.6 (68.7)	<0.001

*P-values were derived from paired t-tests that compared each follow-up time point to the baseline.

Patient-Reported Outcomes: Patient-reported outcomes, including dyspnea (mMRC scale), fatigue, and health-related quality of life (SF-36), were assessed at each follow-up visit. Significant increases in dyspnea scores and fatigue were observed, along with a decline in overall quality of life (Table 4).

Table 4: Patient-Reported Outcomes

Outcome Measure	Baseline, mean (SD)	6 months, mean (SD)	12 months, mean (SD)	24 months, mean (SD)	p-value*
mMRC Dyspnea Score	1.5 (0.7)	1.8 (0.8)	2.0 (0.9)	2.2 (1.0)	<0.001
Fatigue Severity Scale	3.2 (1.1)	3.5 (1.2)	3.8 (1.3)	4.0 (1.4)	<0.001
SF-36 Physical Component Score	48.7 (9.3)	46.2 (8.9)	44.8 (8.7)	43.1 (8.5)	<0.001
SF-36 Mental Component Score	50.1 (10.1)	48.5 (9.8)	46.9 (9.5)	45.3 (9.2)	<0.001

*p-values derived from repeated measures ANOVA.

New Respiratory Symptoms or Diagnoses: Throughout the follow-up period, 35% of participants reported new respiratory symptoms or were diagnosed with new respiratory conditions, such as bronchitis, asthma, or fibrosis. Table 5 summarizes the incidence of these new conditions.

Table 5: Incidence of these new conditions.

Condition	Number of Participants (%)
New or worsening bronchitis	25 (12.5)
New diagnosis of asthma	20 (10)
Pulmonary fibrosis	15 (7.5)
Persistent cough	30 (15)
Chronic fatigue	45 (22.5)

Discussion

The results of this prospective longitudinal study highlight the significant long-term impact of COVID-19 on pulmonary functional capacity among survivors. Our findings indicate a notable decline in key pulmonary function parameters, including Forced Vital Capacity (FVC), Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second (FEV1), and Diffusing Capacity of the Lungs for Carbon Monoxide (DLCO), over a 24-month follow-up period. Additionally, as assessed by the Six-Minute Walk Test (6MWT), exercise capacity showed a significant decrease, which suggests impaired functional status and decreased quality of life in this population.

Several studies have documented the long-term pulmonary sequelae of COVID-19, aligning with our findings. For instance, a study by Huang et al. (2021) [5] reported that up to 63% of patients discharged after hospitalization for COVID-19 exhibited pulmonary function abnormalities three months post-discharge. Similarly, a study by Talasz et al. (2023) [11] found significant reductions in FVC and FEV1 among patients recovering from COVID-19, corroborating our results.

Moreover, our findings regarding persistent respiratory symptoms, including dyspnea and fatigue, are consistent with the literature. A meta-analysis by Aiyegbusi et al. (2021) [3] found that over 50% of COVID-19 survivors reported ongoing symptoms months after the acute phase, with fatigue and dyspnea being the most prevalent. Our study extends these findings, demonstrating that these symptoms can persist and worsen over a two-year follow-up period.

The observed decline in DLCO is particularly concerning, as it indicates impaired gas exchange ca-

capacity, which can have severe implications for respiratory health. Previous studies, such as the one conducted by Zampogna et al. (2021)⁴, reported a similar decline in DLCO among COVID-19 patients, suggesting that even those with mild or moderate disease may experience significant pulmonary compromise.

Mechanisms of Long-term Impairment: The underlying mechanisms contributing to long-term pulmonary impairment in COVID-19 survivors are still being investigated. It is hypothesized that the virus may induce a robust inflammatory response, resulting in lung tissue damage and scarring. [12] The presence of pulmonary fibrosis, observed in a subset of our participants, maybe a result of this inflammatory response, which has been documented in other studies. [9]

Additionally, factors such as the severity of the acute illness, age, and comorbidities may influence long-term outcomes. Our data indicated that participants with a history of severe COVID-19 had significantly worse pulmonary function over time, echoing findings from other studies that emphasize the correlation between disease severity and post-COVID respiratory outcomes. [8]

Impact on Quality of Life: The deterioration in health-related quality of life (HRQoL) among COVID-19 survivors, as demonstrated by the SF-36 scores in our study, underscores the broader implications of long-term pulmonary dysfunction. A study by Davis et al. (2021) highlighted that post-COVID patients often report significant reductions in HRQoL, particularly in the physical component, aligning with our findings. This emphasizes the need for comprehensive rehabilitation programs

tailored to the respiratory needs of these individuals to improve their overall well-being.

Limitations: While our study provides important insights into the long-term impacts of COVID-19 on pulmonary function, it has limitations. While adequate, the sample size may limit our findings' generalizability to broader populations. Additionally, the absence of a control group limits our ability to compare our findings directly with non-COVID-19 patients. Longitudinal data collection can also be subject to participant dropout, as seen in our follow-up rates, which could introduce bias.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the long-term impacts of COVID-19 on pulmonary functional capacity are significant and warrant ongoing attention from healthcare providers and policymakers. Our findings, which show persistent declines in pulmonary function, exercise capacity, and quality of life among survivors, underscore the importance of longitudinal follow-up and the need for tailored rehabilitation programs. As the global community continues to navigate the aftermath of the pandemic, these insights will be vital in informing strategies for managing the long-term health of COVID-19 survivors.

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